

The Influence of User-Generated Content, Conspicuous Consumption, and Flash Sales on Impulsive Buying Behavior E-Commerce with Pay Later as a Moderation Variable

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Abstract:- This study examines how flash sales, conspicuous spending, and user-generated content affect impulsive purchases in e-commerce, using pay later as a moderation variable. This kind of research uses an associative-causal methodology and is quantitative in nature. The study's population consists of an unidentified number of Indonesians who regularly purchase online. In this study, 100 participants served as samples. Non-probability sampling was the method employed for sampling in this investigation. Using SMART PLS 4.0 software, a Structural Equation Model (SEM) technique based on partial Least Square (PLS) was applied for data analysis in this study. The results prove that (1) User-generated content has a significant effect on impulsive buying. (2) Conspicuous consumption has no significant effect on impulsive buying. (3) Flash sales have a significant effect on impulsive buying. (4) Pay later does not strengthen the influence of user-generated content on impulsive buying. (5) Pay later strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying. (6) Pay later strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying.

Keywords:- Consumer Behavior, Impulse Buying, User-Generated Content, Conspicuous Consumption, Flash Sale, Pay Later.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technological developments and changes in consumer behavior have resulted in impulse buying not only being limited to certain product categories. Initially, impulse purchases often occurred in products displayed in front of the cashier, such as candy and chocolate. However, nowadays, impulse purchases often occur in fashion products. This is due to the increasing development of current clothing trends, the phenomenon of impulse buying of fashion by e-commerce consumers has often occurred. With a strong urge to always look trendy and have the latest styles in front of the public, the fashion someone chooses can also show their lifestyle and social status. This shows that in the modern world, lifestyle helps determine attitudes, values and shows social status (Barnard, 2011). Therefore, impulse buying in e-commerce

basically occurs not only due to external stimuli, but also internal factors of the consumer.

In the era of the digital economy, purchasing decisions are based on many things, one of which is the influence of user generated content (UGC), because one way of consumer interaction via social media is with UGC (Kim et al., 2016). User generated content is a form of digital marketing that is widely used by some influencers in order to encourage consumer confidence in purchasing decisions. UGC is a common way to express customers' opinions or expressions about products and provide comparative information regarding the products to be purchased (Dong Ya'nan, et al., 2023). Waskithoadji (2020) said that UGC is a form of digital marketing that has the highest influence on every consumer's purchasing decisions. UGC is said to be a communication medium for consumers to influence and increase impulsive buying through social media in the form of interesting content that recommends an item or product to consumers.

Conspicuous Consumption or conspicuous consumption is a consumption activity carried out not to maximize individual utility functions but for other purposes, namely to impress other people. so that consumers who make conspicuous purchases will buy products not to fulfill their needs, but to show off their wealth to others. According to Jung et al., (2020) conspicuous consumption is associated with values that allow demonstrating greater economic capabilities through products consumed by the public, which results in the consumer's reputation and social status. However, the value of conspicuous consumption behavior can be a barrier to sustainable consumption because the desire to achieve excessive consumption is carried out at all costs.

In this way, it is often pointed out that conspicuous consumption leads to social inequality and hinders sustainability, since this type of consumption attracts people who seek vivid social exposure through the purchase, use and demonstration of products and services that allow them to be socially superior to others. conspicuous consumers often associate sustainable products with products with no design, little aesthetics, very outdated and unattractive; namely with values that do not allow them to achieve social distinction (Jung et al., 2020). As a result, conspicuous consumption to

display one's social status results in consumers making unplanned purchases or impulse buying.

With the increase in shopping through e-commerce, marketers are also making innovations in promoting their products and making it easier for consumers to make purchases at fairly affordable prices. Many digital platforms provide Flash Sale services with lots of discounts as a promotional event to attract consumers. One of the goals of the flash sale program is to create a sense of urgency in the audience to make a purchase so that they will take advantage of the program before the period runs out. This urgency will encourage consumers to behave impulsively buying.

Flash sales are a form of sales that offer products at lower prices than normal prices in limited quantities and for a limited time (Gu et al., 2015). Because flash sales are held at a certain time, purchases are also made at a predetermined time. However, the flash sale sales system is not always used because it is only carried out at certain moments. By offering cheap products but limited by time and number of products, it will influence consumer purchasing behavior.

The current payment system is not only in cash with physical money, and non-cash, but a new payment scheme has emerged with the aim of providing convenience and attracting consumers, namely a payment scheme with the term Buy Now, Pay Later (known as PayLater) as a financial facility that allows payment methods. in installments without a credit card. PayLater makes it easier for consumers to pay for a transaction at a later date, either with a single payment or in installments (Novendra and Aulianisa, 2020). PayLater is an online loan service without a credit card that allows consumers to pay for a transaction at a later date, either with a single payment or in installments. Currently, many e-commerce companies are implementing the PayLater payment method. The pay later payment method makes it easier for individuals to make purchases even in poor financial conditions. This pay later payment method is used as a payment option for a certain period of time, which increases impulse purchases (Parameswari and Ginny, 2022).

Research on impulse buying has been widely carried out by academics. However, there is still little research that elaborates on impulse purchases which are influenced by user generated content, conspicuous consumption and flash sales. Previous research was conducted by Arif et al., (2020) with the results that user generated content had a significant effect on impulsive buying. This research is supported by the research results of Mauludy et al., (2022) which states that user generated content has a significant effect on impulsive buying. The lack of research on UGC on impulsive buying makes it important to carry out further research by adding conspicuous consumption and flash sale variables as the latest research.

Apart from that, the research gap in this research is also the lack of research that explores flash sales as a sales promotion media to encourage impulsive buying in online markets (Martaleni et al., 2022). However, with the development of the internet and the shift in consumer

behavior from traditional purchases to online purchases, marketers need to understand the role of emotions in triggering unplanned purchases in digital applications. Inconsistencies in research results are also a research gap in this research. Research conducted by Wulan (2020), Arestrias & Wijanarko (2021), and Syauqi et al., (2022) found that flash sales had a significant effect on impulsive buying. Meanwhile, different results were found by Martaleni et al., (2022) and Lamis et al., (2022) who found that flash sales did not have a direct significant influence on impulsive buying. This research was conducted to complement previous research by Liu & Lu (2019), and Wu et al. (2021) which focuses more on attitudes towards flash sales as an individual's internal response and attitudes as a mediator between limited time and quantity and impulse buying.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior according to Kotler and Keller (2009) is the study of how individuals, groups and organizations choose, buy, use and how goods, services, ideas or experiences satisfy their needs and desires.

B. Impulse Buying

According to Rook (1987), impulsive buying is a sudden, often strong and persistent urge to buy something immediately. Impulsive buying is a condition of rushing through purchasing activities as if pressed for time, without considering the subsequent consequences after making a purchase. Rook (1987) emphasizes that in impulsive buying, consumers may be in an irrational condition when shopping. Impulsive behavior can occur in any situation, impulse buying can occur every day.

C. User Generated Content

According to Somerfield et al., (2018) user-generated content is the main means used by consumers to express themselves and communicate with other people. Meanwhile, the most frequently cited definition of UGC comes from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), which is 2007, defined UGC as having three main characteristics:

- UGC is content that is publicly available over the Internet;
- UGC is content that reflects a certain amount of creative effort; And
- UGC is content created outside of professional routine and practice.

D. Conspicuous Consumption

According to Bronner & Hoog (2018) Conspicuous consumption is the level of a person's behavioral tendency to display one's social status, wealth, taste or self-image to a reference group through the consumption of products that can be seen by the public. According to Assimos et al., (2019; 353) who state that conspicuous consumption should be seen as a way to increase prestige in society, through public displays of wealth. Then Piron (2020) defines conspicuous consumption as social and public visibility around the consumption of a product. In order for their consumption to

be conspicuous, they do it at social activities that are witnessed by the public and other consumers.

E. Flash Sale

According to Zhang et al., (2018), flash sales have two functions, namely to promote products and increase demand during the sales period. In addition, flash sales can generate greater post-sale product returns for merchants who sell seasonal products (Liu et al., 2021). Several previous literature and research have proven that the flash sale sales promotion strategy provides many benefits not only for consumers but also for sellers because it can help sellers attract more consumers.

F. Pay Later

PayLater is currently an attractive payment scheme option for people who have a limited budget. PayLater is an online loan service without a credit card that makes it easy for consumers to pay for a transaction at a later date, either with a single payment or in installments (Cigna Health & Wellness in Novendra and Aulianisa, 2020). This method is starting to become a digital payment option besides credit/debit cards and mobile transfers, when the need for online credit installments is increasingly needed by the public.

G. The Influence of User Generated Content on Impulse Buying

User generated content is the main means that consumers use to express themselves and communicate with other people (friends or other users they do not know but use the same social media platform) in modern society (Boyd and Ellison, 2008). UGC refers to media content created by members of the general public and includes any form of online content created, initiated, circulated, and consumed by users (Daugherty et al., 2008). UGC drives product awareness and influences consumer purchasing decisions (Blakley, 2013). Most consumers rely on other people's experiences by visiting social media to shop online through e-commerce using different devices, such as mobile phones, tablets, and computers. The online shopping environment for customers is shaped by social connectivity, opinion leaders, and online recommendations. Research conducted by Mauludy et al., (2022), states that user generated content contributes significantly to impulsive buying and purchase intention.

H1: User generated content has a significant effect on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce.

H. The Effect of Conspicuous Consumption on Impulse Buying

According to Roy Chaudhuri et al., (2011), conspicuous consumption is the deliberate engagement in the purchase, ownership and use of symbolic and visible products and services, imbued with scarce economic and cultural capital with the motivation to communicate a distinctive self-image to other people. Conspicuous consumption refers to the display of excessive spending of money on goods or services to signal one's wealth and social status (Veblen, 2009). People tend to spend a lot on products for reasons of gaining social recognition, enhancing self-image, and signaling prestige to others (Shukla, 2008). Therefore, with the large number of exhibition events that are held, it will give rise to impulsive

buying because a group of people are not aware that they are being influenced to immediately make purchases without prior planning.

H2: Conspicuous Consumption has a significant effect on impulsive buying.

I. The Effect of Flash Sales on Impulse Buying

The flash sale e-commerce model is an online distribution channel that offers various products or services at big discounts for a limited period and perhaps the products are also limited. So, it has proven effective in attracting consumers in large numbers who are sensitive to prices and discounts. For e-commerce platforms that adopt the flash sale model, there are quite a few advantages. Flash sales have a combination of limited time and deep discount features that can trigger consumer impulse purchases (Berezina et al., 2016). In addition, the limited execution of the flash sale strategy aims to create a sense of urgency, thereby triggering impulse purchases (Chan et al., 2017). Apart from that, flash sales can also stimulate consumers' desire to buy, so that consumers think that the products being sold are unique and difficult to find.

H3: Flash sales have a significant effect on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce.

J. The Influence of User Generated Content, Conspicuous Consumption, and Flash Sale on Impulse Buying with PayLater as a Moderating Variable

PayLater is an online loan method that can be done without a credit card and is currently becoming an attractive payment option for people who have a limited budget. PayLater makes it easy for consumers to pay for transactions at a later date, either with a single payment or in installments (Novendra and Aulianisa, 2020). With the convenience provided, it is possible that PayLater will be used more by consumers, according to research results by Putri and Iriani (2020) where the ease of using online loan services (PayLater) can have a positive effect on impulsive purchases. Furthermore, research from Prameswari and Ginny (2022) states that paylater is able to increase impulse purchases. PayLater allows for increased profits as it drives increased merchant sales, potentially impulsively generating high merchant fees as commissions to lenders (Guttman-Kenney and Gathergood, 2022). Several studies have been conducted examining PayLater, but there has been no more specific research on how strong PayLater's influence is in moderating impulsive buying behavior.

H4: PayLater strengthens the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce

H5: PayLater strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce

H6: PayLater strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Google Forms is an online questionnaire tool that was used to collect research data. Regarding gender, age, education, employment, income, area, and the kind of pay subsequently utilized for buying, respondents' demographics were varied. After using purposive sampling as a sample

strategy, 100 Indonesian respondents who have made online purchases were given the questionnaire. This study's data analysis employed clever PLS 4.0 software to perform a variance-based structural equation test utilizing the partial Least Square (PLS) SEM approach. Based on the SEM-PLS model's data features, which allow for low error rates in identification and testing even with a small sample size, the PLS approach was selected for this study.

Respondent characteristics: Because the study used an online questionnaire form, 100 respondents completed it. Because of this, all questions on the form could be required to be answered in order for all respondents to provide their comprehensive replies. The following attributes of research participants differed widely:

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

Items	Classifications	Number of People	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	41	41%
	Women	59	59%
Ages	18 – 25	73	73%
	26 – 34	27	27%
Job	Students	20	20%
	Entrepreneur	18	18%
	ASN	5	5%
	Private employee	37	37%
	Etc	20	20%
Education	High Svchool	19	19%
	Diploma/S1	74	74%
	S2	7	7%
Income	≤ Rp. 1.500.000	35	35%
	Rp. 1.500.000 s/d 3.000.000	35	35%
	Rp. 10.100.000 s/d 20.000.000	1	1%
	Rp. 20.000.000 ≥	2	2%
Types of e-commerce visited	Lombok Island	80	80%
	Sumbawa Island	10	10%
	Jawa Island	10	10%
Types of e-commerce visited	Shopee Paylater	65	65%
	Akulaku	24	24%
	Kredivo	9	9%
	Lainnya	2	2%

The results of the item reliability test are presented in the table. It can be seen from the table that all indicators of this research variable have factor loading values greater than 0.70 (Hair, 2010). All items are said to be valid and used to test this research model.

The results of the discriminant validity test were carried out using the AVE value. The first condition must be met at this testing stage, and the AVE value must be greater than 0.5.

Table 2. Validity Test Results

User Generated Content (X1)	r Hitung	r Table	Ket.
User-generated content describes the function of a fashion product	0,827	0,5	Valid
User-generated content illustrates the advantages of fashion products	0,854	0,5	Valid
User-generated content illustrates the value of fashion products	0,930	0,5	Valid
User-generated content creates a positive atmosphere towards fashion products	0,836	0,5	Valid
User-generated content creates positive emotions towards fashion products	0,803	0,5	Valid
User-generated content creates positive feelings towards fashion products	0,855	0,5	Valid
User-generated content makes me interested in fashion products	0,840	0,5	Valid
Conspicuous Consumption (X2)	r Hitung	r Table	Ket.
I purchase fashion products to show my success.	0,805	0,5	Valid
I purchase fashion products to be respected by others	0,880	0,5	Valid
I purchase fashion products to improve my social status	0,809	0,5	Valid
I purchase fashion products to show a unique experience that is not shared by others.	0,766	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products because they are trendy	0,760	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products because I want to show my identity	0,652	0,5	Valid
Flash Sale (X3)	r Hitung	r Table	Ket.
Fashion products available in flash sales are limited in quantity	0,553	0,5	Valid

Fashion products available in flash sales sell out quickly	0,756	0,5	Valid
Flash sales provide limited shopping time	0,540	0,5	Valid
Flash sales provide a short shopping time	0,405	0,5	Tidak Valid
Flash sales provide relevant fashion product information	0,908	0,5	Valid
Flash sale provides short shopping time Flash sale provides accurate fashion product information	0,918	0,5	Valid
Flash sales provide information on the latest fashion products	0,911	0,5	Valid
Flash sales provide fashion products at affordable prices	0,831	0,5	Valid
Flash sales provide discounts on fashion products offered	0,759	0,5	Valid
Flash sale provides free shipping on every fashion product	0,840	0,5	Valid
Pay Later helped me get the product I wanted. (Z)	r Hitung	r Table	Ket.
<i>Pay Later helped me get the product I wanted.</i>	0,879	0,5	Valid
Faster verification of approval to use the Pay Later feature.	0,930	0,5	Valid
I find it easy when transacting using Pay Later.	0,849	0,5	Valid
I did not find it difficult to use the Pay Later feature.	0,759	0,5	Valid
I feel safe when transacting using Pay Later.	0,874	0,5	Valid
I can afford to pay my bills using the Pay Later feature.	0,799	0,5	Valid
Payments with the Pay Later feature can be made with a flexible instalment period.	0,865	0,5	Valid
Impulse Buying	r Hitung	r Table	Ket.
I make spontaneous purchases of fashion products on e-commerce.	0,870	0,5	Valid
I make purchases of fashion products without evaluating the product first	0,760	0,5	Valid
I make purchases of fashion products without looking for other alternative options	0,824	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products on e-commerce without planning	0,864	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products according to my wishes	0,698	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products without thinking about the consequences	0,847	0,5	Valid
I can't stop myself from shopping	0,905	0,5	Valid
I buy fashion products because of the urge to shop	0,863	0,5	Valid

Based on the validity test results in the table above, it shows that there is 1 (one) statement item X3.4. which is invalid, namely in the flash sale variable. This statement item is then eliminated from the statement items on the limited time scarcity indicator. Meanwhile, the other statement items can be fully said to be valid because they have a value of r count ≥ 0.5 . This is in accordance with the opinion of Hair (2010) which states that an item is said to have a significant relationship with its construct if the item has a loading value (loading factor) of more than 0.5. This means that items that have a loading factor below 0.5 will be removed from the construct so that the items that make up the construct are only items that have a loading factor greater than or equal to 0.5. In the PLS SEM approach, a measurement has met convergent validity if it meets several conditions (Hair et al, 2010). According to Hair et al., (2010) the minimum value of each loading factor with a value ≥ 0.5 .

IV. RESULTS

This research uses a Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis that was stated previously. Hypothesis testing can be done through t-statistic values and probability values through Bootstrapping which can be seen in the following figure:

Fig 1. Path Coefficient

Table 4. Hypothesis Test Results

Relations	T Statistic	P Value	
User Generated Content -> Impulsive buying	1,995	0,047	Significant
Conspicuous Consumption -> Impulsive buying	1,689	0,092	Not Significant
Flash Sale -> Impulsive buying	5,549	0,000	Significant
User Generated Content. Paylater -> Impulsive buying	0,051	0,959	Not Significant
Conspicuous Consumption. Paylater -> Impulsive buying	2,837	0,005	Significant
Flash Sale. Paylater -> Impulsive buying	2,090	0,037	Significant

Based on table 4 above it can be explained as follows:

a. H1: User generated content has a significant effect on impulsive buying.

The influence of the user generated content variable on impulsive buying has a t-statistic greater than 1.96 and a P value less than 0.05. This shows that the user generated content variable has a positive and significant influence on the impulsive buying variable, so that Hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted.

b. H2: Conspicuous consumption has no significant effect on impulsive buying.

The influence of the conspicuous consumption variable on impulsive buying has a t-statistic smaller than 1.96 and a P value greater than 0.05. This shows that the conspicuous consumption variable has a positive but not significant influence on the impulsive buying variable, so Hypothesis 2 (H2) is rejected.

c. H3: Flash sales have a significant effect on impulsive buying.

The influence of the flash sale variable on impulsive buying has a t-statistic greater than 1.96 and a P value less than 0.05. This shows that the flash sale variable has a positive and significant influence on the impulsive buying variable, so that Hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted.

d. H4: Pay later does not strengthen the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying.

The paylater variable does not strengthen the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying which has a t-statistic value smaller than 1.96 and a P value greater than 0.05. This shows that the paylater variable has a positive but not significant relationship in strengthening the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying, so Hypothesis 4 (H4) is rejected.

e. H5: Pay later strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying.

The paylater variable strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying, having a t-statistic greater than 1.96 and a P value of less than 0.05. This shows that the pay later variable has a positive and significant influence in strengthening the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying, so that Hypothesis 5 (H5) is accepted.

f. H6: Pay later strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying.

The paylater variable strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying, having a t-statistic greater than 1.96 and a P value of less than 0.05. This shows that the pay later variable has a positive and significant influence in strengthening the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying, so that Hypothesis 6 (H6) is accepted.

V. DISCUSSION

User generated content has an influence on consumer impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce in Indonesia. User generated content is defined as the main means used by consumers to express themselves and communicate with others (Sommerfield et al., 2018). Various forms of UGC are online reviews, posts on social media, text, video blogs, ratings of a product. Apart from that, UGC can also shape a person's attitude towards shopping because most consumers depend on other people's experiences. Various forms of UGC are online consumer reviews through social media posts, text, video vlogs, and rating products. By exploring the market place, consumers can imagine their needs and carry out impulsive buying and do not have specific shopping goals at the start (Zhang et al., 2018). A lot of information about products is obtained through user-generated content, so UGC has become the main element for creating emotional responses and encouraging impulse purchases (Kim & Johnson, 2016). Impulsive buying is also referred to as the urge to buy a product that is presented to them, without any consideration or reason for buying the product. Human behavior that is processed unconsciously and is known to be unplanned, is also a response that is produced after a stimulus (Jeffery & Hodge, 2007). In an online context when people view UGC, they imagine the use and outcome of the product or service which could lead to a purchase (To et al., 2007). The impact of UGC can result in impulsive purchasing decisions. This is supported by the research results of Mauludy et al., (2022), stating that user generated content contributes significantly to impulsive buying and purchase intention. So UGC has a significant effect on impulsive buying.

Conspicuous consumption does not have a strong influence on consumer impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce in Indonesia. Conspicuous consumption is a consumptive behavior in which the act of spending money on luxurious or expensive things that are not important to impress other people with the aim of showing off to other people. This consumer behavior is irrational because it is only strongly driven by the desire to look different without looking at aspects of need. So conspicuous consumption is often associated with the recent flexing phenomenon, especially in the world of social media where more and more people openly

show off their wealth for various purposes to the public. They consume and use various luxury facilities, such as bags, clothes, cars, jewelry, and even luxury vacations. The results of previous research by Ferman & Benli (2019) and Chandra (2020) stated that conspicuous consumption has a significant influence on impulsive buying behavior. However, the results of this research do not strengthen previous research where conspicuous consumption did not have a significant effect on impulse buying in e-commerce. There are several factors that cause the results of this research to be insignificant, namely that the average monthly income of respondents is dominated by the middle class, so they tend to plan in advance before purchasing luxury goods. Apart from that, respondents also did not make flashy purchases just to show off the success they had achieved. The results of this research are more directed towards the conventional concept, the purpose of consumption is to satisfy needs and desires (utility). Consumers tend to be rational in making choices. They consider price and income before deciding to buy a product.

Flash sales have a significant influence on impulsive buying behavior in e-commerce in Indonesia. Flash sale is defined as an online distribution channel that offers various products or services in the form of promotions and discounts within a limited time period and the products are also limited too. Flash sales are an element that has proven effective in attracting consumers who are sensitive to prices and discounts. This promotion can stimulate consumers' desire to buy, so that consumers think that the products being sold are unique and difficult to find. Flash sales have a combination of limited time and deep discount features that can trigger consumer impulse purchases (Berezina et al., 2016). In addition, the limited execution of the flash sale strategy aims to create a sense of urgency, thereby triggering impulse purchases (Chan et al., 2017). Previous research conducted by Zakiyyah (2018) found that impulsive buying behavior occurs when flash sales are offered, as evidenced by 69% of respondents immediately deciding to make a purchase right then and there when they saw the product photo and found out product specification information. Consumers tend not to be able to control themselves when making purchases and are more likely to be impulsive buyers in e-commerce. These results strengthen research conducted by Zhang (2018) which states that flash sales encourage consumers to make impulse purchases. More specifically, it is said that flash sales, by providing significant price discounts and short holding times, build a perception of scarcity of goods and create a perception of high value of goods, thus causing impulse purchases. So it can be said that flash sales have a significant relationship with impulse buying.

Pay later does not strengthen the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying. Although in the first hypothesis user generated content has a significant influence on impulsive buying in e-commerce. Paylater is known as an online loan service that can be used directly on e-commerce or online shopping applications. User generated content focuses on the consumer dimension, where content is created by the general public and then distributed on social media. Consumers contribute to content creation in various ways, such as providing positive or negative reviews of products,

creating vlogs and texts that provide a lot of information about a product. The content created becomes a marketing communication medium between consumers and marketers. Sometimes people cannot differentiate between content created by marketers or experienced consumers. However, through UGC consumers may participate in content creation for a variety of reasons, including the notion that consumers are encouraged to create their own advertising for self-promotion or intrinsic enjoyment or in the hope of changing public perception. With various conveniences in using this service, paylater has a positive influence on impulse buying behavior (Putri and Iriani, 2020). Apart from that, Prameswari and Ginny (2022) also stated that paylaters are able to increase impulse purchases. However, the results are different in this research in that paylater does not strengthen the influence of user generated content on impulsive buying.

Pay later strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying. Conspicuous consumption is the level of a person's behavioral tendency to display one's social status, wealth, taste or self-image to a reference group through the consumption of products that can be seen publicly (Bronner & de Hoog, 2018). They make purchases to demonstrate their social prestige, rather than to meet their basic needs. Likewise, individuals spend conspicuously to demonstrate their wealth. Conspicuous consumption refers to individuals aiming for access to a higher social class using excessive spending. Charoennan (2018) states that conspicuous consumption can be accelerated by an application because the more consumers use an application media, the higher the impulsive buying behavior for a product. With technological developments, e-commerce has become a market that is very easy to use and accessible to everyone. Where shopping no longer requires going to the market or shop, but can be accessed anywhere. Therefore, paylater is able to strengthen the relationship between conspicuous consumption and impulsive buying in e-commerce.

Pay later strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying. Flash sales are short sales that are part of sales promotions that provide special offers or discounts for certain products for a limited time and also limited products. Flash sales on e-commerce in Indonesia are often held at certain times and also on certain products and not all products in these stores are included in the flash sale program.

Consumers who do not control themselves to make unplanned purchases are more likely to become impulse buyers. With so many attributes in e-commerce, it is an important factor in responding to customer behavior. So to increase impulse purchases online, easy access to e-commerce and flash sale programs are widely implemented by every seller. Almost all the time there are always products available in the flash sale category. This is what influences consumers to shop without evaluating first and without planning because of attractive discounts. Currently, consumers are very sensitive to price because it can influence purchasing decisions that lead to impulsive purchases. Pay Later is currently an attractive payment scheme option for

people who have a limited budget. PayLater is an online loan service without a credit card that makes it easy for consumers to pay for a transaction at a later date, either with a single payment or in installments. When many shops offer flash sales on e-commerce, consumers no longer worry about not being able to get products in cash. The paylater payment method makes it easy to get products. Therefore, paylater is able to strengthen the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research analysis and the results of the discussion in the previous chapter, the conclusions of this research are as follows: (1) User-generated content has a significant effect on impulsive buying. (2) Conspicuous consumption has no significant effect on impulsive buying. (3) Flash sales have a significant effect on impulsive buying. (4) Pay later does not strengthen the influence of user-generated content on impulsive buying. (5) Pay later strengthens the influence of conspicuous consumption on impulsive buying. (6) Pay later strengthens the influence of flash sales on impulsive buying.

The managerial implications of this research are managers need to understand the importance of creating a buying atmosphere that prioritizes wants over needs. Giving bonus shopping vouchers with a certain usage time limit is an important strategy to increase impulsive buying, provoke consumer interest, and create shopping urgency. Managers should be judicious in determining the products covered by the vouchers to maximize profits. Promotion through social media with innovative advertisements requires continuous and persuasive management to create a strong purchase stimulus.

Future research can also elaborate on other variables to enrich research results such as linking Fear of Missing Out (FoMo) and Hedonist behavior with impulsive buying, because research on FoMo always leads to the field of psychology, in the context of using the internet and social media for purchasing behavior. This FoMo behavior forms a must-do behavior that goes hand in hand with must-have, where buying behavior is due to fear of missing out on trends and limited products.

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